

**Learning Styles of the College Students of a
Filipino-Chinese School in Iloilo City, Philippines**

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Abstract

In a learner-centered educational environment, understanding of the learning styles of students is necessary. It is believed that customization of learning materials and learning activities according to types of learners enhances learning outcomes. Among the available literatures about learning styles is that of Grasha and Reichmann. The Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale consists of 60 statements that determine the six learning dimensions, namely: independent, avoidant, collaborative, dependent, competitive, and participant. This study was conducted to determine the learning styles of the college students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc. The results of this study would add to the collection of profile of students, since the college department is still in its early years. All of the college students enrolled in the second semester of academic year 2014-2015 were considered in this study. Students when taken as a whole or grouped according to sex or year level are moderate as to the following dimensions: independent, dependent, and participant. Students when taken as a whole or grouped according to sex and year level are high as to the following dimensions: collaborative and competitive. As to the avoidant dimension, students when taken as a whole or grouped according to sex are high. In addition, the first year students are also high, but the second year students are moderate.

Keywords: learning styles, Grasha-Reichmann scale, learning style dimensions, Chinese school, Hua Siong

Introduction

“Students learn in different ways” (Felder, 2002). This takes into consideration that every person is unique. Such uniqueness applies in the different aspects of human beings. Students’ learning preferences varies.

Sternberg (as cited in Hatami, 2012) described learning style as a preferred way of using one’s ability and not in itself as ability. Learning style can also be described as a set of factors, behaviors, and attitudes that facilitate learning for an individual in a given situation (“What are Learning Styles”, n.d.).

Different instruments are available in order to measure one’s learning styles. Learning styles may be measured in different ways. One of the instruments is the Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale (GRSLSS).

The GRSLSS was developed by Anthony Grasha and Sheryl Reichmann. It is associated with three classroom dimensions: student attitudes towards learning, their views of their teachers and peers, and their reactions to classroom procedures (Grasha, 1996). Spanning six categories, GRSLSS promotes understanding of learning in a broad context: competitive, collaborative, avoidant, participant, dependent, and independent. Competitive students learn materials in order to perform better than others in the class. Students with this style prefer to become a group leader in discussions, be singled out in class for doing good job, and dominate class discussions. Collaborative students feel they can learn by sharing ideas and talents. These students prefer lectures with small group discussion, student-centered aspects of courses, and group rather than individual projects. Avoidant students are not enthusiastic about learning content and attending the class. They are generally turned off by most classroom activities, prefer no tests and blanket grades where everyone gets a passing grade, and do not like enthusiastic teachers. Participants are good citizens in the class. These learners prefer discussion, class reading of assignments, and teachers who can analyse and synthesize information. Dependent learners show little intellectual curiosity and they learn only what is required. These students who are dependent prefer outlines or notes on the board, clear deadlines and instructions for assignments, teacher-centered methods, and little ambiguity as possible in all aspects of the course. Independent learners like to think for themselves and are confident in their learning abilities. This type of students prefers independent study, working alone, self-paced instruction, and student-centered rather than teacher-centered approach (Grasha & Hruska, 1989).

The researchers believe that knowing students' learning styles may help teachers prepare relevant activities to enhance the learning of students; hence, they conducted this study. Moreover, the results of this study would add to the collection of profile of students, since the college department is still in its early years.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The independent variables were sex and year level, while the dependent variables were the learning styles in the following dimensions: competitive, collaborative, avoidant, participant, dependent, and independent.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Statement of the Problem and Hypotheses

This study was conducted to determine the learning styles of the college students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc., Philippines. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

1. What are the learning styles of the students when they are taken as a whole?
2. What are the learning styles of the students when they are grouped according to sex?
3. What are the learning styles of the students when they are grouped according to year level?

Methodology

Quantitative-descriptive research design was employed in this study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the 36 students, representing all officially enrolled college students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc., during the second semester, academic year 2014-2015.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents. In terms of sex, 61% were female while 39% were male. As to year level, 56% were first year level while 44% were second year level.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Category	N	%
Entire Group	36	100
Sex		
Female	22	61
Male	14	39
Year Level		
1 st Year	20	56
2 nd Year	16	44

Instrumentation

The Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale (GRSLSS) composed of 60 statements was utilized in this study. Ten (10) statements correspond to measuring each of the learning style dimensions, namely: independent, avoidant, collaborative, dependent, competitive, and participant. Statements number 1, 7, 13, 19, 25, 31, 27, 43, 49, and 55 cover independent dimension. Statements number 2, 8, 14, 20, 26, 32, 38, 44, 50, and 56 measure avoidant

dimension. Statements number 3, 9, 15, 21, 27, 33, 39, 45, 51, and 57 quantify collaborative dimension. Statements number 4, 10, 16, 22, 28, 34, 40, 46, 52, and 58 measure dependent dimension. Statements number 5, 11, 17, 23, 29, 35, 41, 47, 53, and 59 cover competitive dimension. While, statements number 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54, and 60 measure participant dimension. Each statement is answerable by strongly disagree, moderately disagree, undecided, moderately agree, and strongly agree with the weight of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively (Grasha & Hruska, 1989). The average of each of the dimensions obtained from the responses of every respondent was used in the data processing.

To describe the learning styles of the students, the following scale was adopted.

	Low	Moderate	High
Independent	1.0-2.7	2.8-3.8	3.9-5.0
Avoidant	1.0-1.8	1.9-3.1	3.2-5.0
Collaborative	1.0-2.7	2.8-3.4	3.5-5.0
Dependent	1.0-2.9	3.0-4.0	4.1-5.0
Competitive	1.0-1.7	1.8-2.8	2.9-5.0
Participant	1.0-3.0	3.1-4.1	4.2-5.0

Performing the reliability test on the GRSLSS using the data from the respondents, the obtained Cronbach's alpha values were as follows: 0.753 (0.746 based on standardized items) for independent, 0.532 (0.493 based on standardized items) for avoidant, 0.625 (0.652 based on standardized items) for collaborative, 0.560 (0.622 based on standardize items) for dependent, 0.629 (0.624 based on standardized items) for competitive, and 0.671 (0.666 based on standardized items) for participant. This shows that the inventory applied in this study possessed high measures of internal consistency.

Data Analysis

This study used the Cronbach's alpha, mean, and standard deviation statistical tools. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instruments based on the responses of the students. While mean and standard deviation were used to present descriptive statistics.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the learning styles of students when taken as an entire group. Students when taken as a whole were moderate as to independent, dependent, and participant; while, they were high as to avoidant, collaborative, and competitive.

Table 2
Learning Styles of Students when Taken as an Entire Group

Learning Style	<i>M (SD)</i>	Description
Independent	3.6 (0.54)	Moderate
Avoidant	3.3 (0.52)	High
Collaborative	3.8 (0.42)	High
Dependent	3.7 (0.41)	Moderate
Competitive	3.4 (0.52)	High
Participant	3.7 (0.48)	Moderate

Table 3 shows the learning styles of students when grouped according to sex. Female and male students were moderate in terms of independent, dependent, and participant; while, they were high as to avoidant, collaborative, and competitive.

Table 3
Learning Styles of Students when Grouped according to Sex

Learning Style	Female		Male	
	<i>M (SD)</i>	Description	<i>M (SD)</i>	Description
Independent	3.6 (0.49)	Moderate	3.7 (0.61)	Moderate
Avoidant	3.3 (0.47)	High	3.2 (0.60)	High
Collaborative	3.8 (0.47)	High	3.8 (0.36)	High
Dependent	3.7 (0.45)	Moderate	3.8 (0.37)	Moderate
Competitive	3.2 (0.49)	High	3.5 (0.54)	High
Participant	3.6 (0.47)	Moderate	3.8 (0.50)	Moderate

Table 4 shows the learning styles of students when classified according to year level. On the one hand, first year students were moderate in terms of independent, dependent, and participant; while, they were high as to avoidant, collaborative, and competitive. On the other hand, male students were moderate as to independent, avoidant, dependent, and participant; while, they were high in terms of collaborative and competitive.

Table 4
Learning Styles of Students when Grouped according to Year Level

Learning Style	First Year		Second Year	
	<i>M (SD)</i>	Description	<i>M (SD)</i>	Description
Independent	3.6 (0.65)	Moderate	3.6 (0.38)	Moderate
Avoidant	3.4 (0.58)	High	3.1 (0.35)	Moderate
Collaborative	3.7 (0.47)	High	3.9 (0.35)	High
Dependent	3.7 (0.46)	Moderate	3.8 (0.35)	Moderate
Competitive	3.4 (0.62)	High	3.3 (0.38)	High
Participant	3.7 (0.55)	Moderate	3.7 (0.40)	Moderate

Conclusions

Students when taken as an entire group possess varying learning styles. Taking into consideration the six dimensions of the learning styles identified in the adopted instrument, each student's exhibits the six dimensions but of different levels.

Regardless of sex, students' learning styles seem the same in which the level in each dimension of the learning styles identified is not the same as compared to every other dimension.

When grouped according to year level, students' learning styles seem different. They are the same only in terms of independent, collaborative, dependent, competitive, and participant; but, they are different as to avoidant. First year students are seem higher as to avoidant dimension as compared with the second year students.

Recommendations

Teachers may consider the results of this study in preparing corresponding learning activities in their respective classes.

Researchers may further the investigation by administering the same instrument every year and find out the difference in the learning styles of the students as they move to higher level.

Researchers may conduct similar studies involving other variables and taking into consideration other learning style inventories. Further, they may conduct a study about learning preferences and learning activities.

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